

FIRM LEVERAGE AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE: A STUDY OF INDUSTRIAL GOODS FIRMS IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *The study determined the effect of firm leverage on financial performance of Nigerian Industrial goods firm. The study used debt-equity ratio as the independent variable and return on assets and return on equity was used as the dependent variables. The study adopted Ex Post-Facto research design. Data were sources from the eight industrial goods firms in Nigeria used for the study spanning from 2013 to 2024. Regression analysis was employed to test the two hypotheses. From the analysis, the study indicates that debt-equity ratio has positive significant effect on return on assets. Another finding showed that debt-equity ratio has negative significant effect on net profit margin of Nigerian industrial goods firm. Based on the findings, the study recommended among others that there is need to implement cost-saving measures to reduce expenses and increase profitability, as well secure low-interest debt to minimize interest expenses and maximize returns.*

Introduction

Most investors prefer persistent increase in the value of their shares in the stock market in order to earn more return on their investments and maximize their wealth. Financial leverage is a measure of how much a firm uses equity and debt to finance its assets. As debt increases, financial leverage increases (Will, 2021). Financial leverage is the degree to which Companies employ debt in their capital structure. Increase in the use of debt in a firm's capital structure increases the risk of financial

distress and probability of bankruptcy which may arise as a result of default. There are certain benefits and costs associated with usage of debt financing. Companies can take advantage of tax shields benefits of debt by employing debt in their capital structure. Interest on debt is tax deductible and the use of debt in a firm's capital structure, unlike equity, does not lead to dilution of ownership. However, they are certain costs associated with debt financing vis-à-vis fixed interest payments, cost of financial distress and bankruptcy costs

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arising from inability of Companies to meet up with their debt obligations as at when due. Companies are therefore, expected to trade-off the benefits of debts against its costs in order to improve financial performance (Abubakar & Garba 2019).

The effect of financial leverage on firm performance has been a controversial issue in corporate finance literature since the seminal work of Modigliani and Miller in 1958 which asserted irrelevance of debt-to- equity ratio for firm value. However, since they considered the assumptions of perfect markets, with no taxes, absence of transaction and bankruptcy costs, the theory about the debt irrelevance became unrealistic. Companies with higher leverage are mostly inclined to improve their performance. However, higher leverage usually leads to higher agency costs because of the diverging interests between shareholders and debt holders. Thus, leverage may negatively affect performance. Furthermore, having debt in a firm's capital structure is beneficial to a firm; this is because a firm with debt in its capital structure enjoys tax savings as interest is paid before tax is deducted from the firm's income. Financial experts also state that financial leverage is a financial tool that is widely used to improve a firm's rate of return and its performance (Adam, 2021).

In today's highly competitive and rapidly evolving global economy, firm performance has become a central focus for stakeholders seeking sustainable growth, profitability, and market

leadership. Firm performance encompasses a wide range of indicators, including profitability, productivity, operational efficiency, market share, and customer satisfaction. For manufacturing firms like Industrial goods, performance is influenced by both internal factors—such as financial management, technological capabilities, human resource practices, and production efficiency—and external factors like market dynamics, regulatory frameworks, inflation, and supply chain disruptions (Afolabi & Laseinde, 2021). In recent years, the Nigerian business environment has experienced substantial volatility due to fluctuating exchange rates, inflationary pressures, and inconsistent government policies. These factors present both challenges and opportunities for manufacturing firms to innovate and adopt strategic practices that drive performance and ensure sustainability (Nwankwo & Uche, 2023).

As a large-scale industrial operation, its performance has a ripple effect on suppliers, distributors, and local employment. Despite its scale and significance, there remains a need for in-depth analysis of the specific determinants of firm performance at the plant level. Issues such as capacity utilization, cost control, financial leverage, investment in technology, and human capital development all play a role in influencing the plant's performance outcomes (Udo & Akpan, 2022). While Industrial goods firm has invested in modern equipment,

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employee training, and expansion projects at the Industrial goods firm, questions remain about how effectively these investments translate into measurable performance improvements. Understanding the dynamics of firm performance within this context is essential for identifying best practices, addressing operational bottlenecks, and ensuring that strategic decisions are data-driven and aligned with long-term goals. Moreover, insights from such a study could offer valuable guidance to other manufacturing firms operating under similar conditions in Nigeria (Okoye & Ezeaku, 2022).

In Nigeria's dynamic industrial sector, financial leverage is increasingly recognized as a critical factor influencing firm performance, sustainability, and competitiveness. The Industrial capital-intensive operations rely on strategic financing decisions to maintain production efficiency, expand market share, and maximize shareholder value. Financial leverage defined as the use of debt in a firm's capital structure can influence profitability, return on investment, and long-term viability. However, the direct impact of financial leverage on the performance of the Industrial goods firm remains underexplored in empirical literature (Okoye & Ezeaku, 2022). Financial leverage offers both opportunities and risks. On one hand, it can amplify returns through tax advantages and enhanced capital availability; on the other, excessive leverage can increase the

risk of financial distress, especially in volatile economic environments like Nigeria's.

Although prior studies have investigated the general relationship between capital structure and firm performance in Nigeria, Most of the prior studies used other manufacturing firms, oil and gas, consumer goods, health care, pharmaceutical firms and so on. There is a dearth research on financial leverage and financial performance on industrial goods firms, except the study of Lawani, *et al* (2023) whose financial data ended in 2022. This study set to fill the gaps, by updating the present study to 2024.

The main objective of the study is to ascertain the effect of financial leverage on financial performance of listed Nigerian Industrial goods firm. The specific objectives are to examine the effect of debt-equity ratio on return on asset and return on equity of listed Industrial goods firm in Nigeria.

Conceptual Reviews

Financial Leverage

Financial leverage is grounded in classical finance theories, including Modigliani and Miller's (1958) capital structure theory, which posits that under certain conditions, the value of a firm is independent of its capital structure. However, when market imperfections such as taxes, bankruptcy costs, and agency problems are considered, the optimal capital structure becomes a central focus for maximizing firm value. The trade-off theory suggests that firms

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balance the tax advantages of debt with the costs of financial distress, while the pecking order theory emphasizes a preference for internal financing over external debt due to information asymmetry (Frank & Goyal, 2022). Firms often rely on a mix of internal and external financing to meet capital needs, particularly in periods of economic uncertainty or inflationary pressure. Research indicates that appropriate leverage levels can help manufacturing firms finance technological upgrades, increase production capacity, and improve competitiveness (Okonkwo & Eze, 2021). However, excessive reliance on debt can expose firms to high interest burdens and liquidity risks, affecting long-term sustainability.

Prior studies have consistently explored the relationship between financial leverage and firm performance, though results are often mixed and industry-specific. While some research finds a positive correlation suggesting that debt financing can lead to improved performance through efficient capital allocation and tax shields (Adegbite & Oluwatosin, 2020) others report a negative relationship, where high debt levels result in financial distress, reduced profitability, and lower market value (Oladeji & Babalola, 2021). In recent years, companies have also turned to financial modeling, scenario analysis, and stress testing to evaluate the potential outcomes of leverage decisions under various economic conditions (Khan & Ali,

2023). Moreover, regulatory frameworks and credit rating systems influence a firm's access to debt markets and the cost of borrowing, further affecting leverage strategy.

Debt-Equity Ratio

Debt financing refers to the process through which a firm raises capital by borrowing, typically through instruments such as loans, bonds, debentures, or credit facilities, with the promise to repay the principal amount along with interest within an agreed timeframe (Ross, Westerfield & Jordan, 2022). One of the primary advantages of debt financing is the tax shield it provides. Interest payments on debt are tax-deductible, effectively lowering the company's taxable income and enhancing after-tax earnings (Damodaran, 2023). This makes debt an attractive source of funding for firms seeking to optimize their capital structure and reduce the cost of capital.

Debt financing plays a significant role in influencing firm performance, especially when used efficiently. Empirical studies suggest that a moderate level of debt can improve firm value by disciplining management and reducing agency costs. However, excessive reliance on debt may lead to financial distress, increased bankruptcy risk, and reduced investor confidence (Afolabi & Laseinde, 2022). The rise of green bonds and Islamic financing instruments in emerging markets has expanded the landscape of debt options available to firms,

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promoting sustainability and ethical financial practices (Yusuf & Bello, 2022).

However, equity financing is a method of raising capital by selling ownership shares in a company, typically in the form of common or preferred stock. Unlike debt financing, which requires regular repayments and interest, equity financing involves no obligation to repay investors. Instead, investors receive a share of ownership and may benefit through dividends and capital appreciation (Brealey, Myers & Allen, 2023). However, equity financing also comes with certain trade-offs, primarily the dilution of ownership and control. Issuing new shares reduces the percentage of ownership for existing shareholders, potentially weakening control over strategic decisions (Rahman & Adenuga, 2023). Moreover, the pressure to meet shareholder expectations, particularly in public companies, may lead to short-termism and influence corporate policies. The debt-to-equity (D/E) ratio is calculated by dividing a company's total liabilities by its shareholder equity. These numbers are available on the statement of financial position of a company's financial statements.

Firm's Performance

Firm's performance is a multi-dimensional concept that reflects how well an organization achieves its objectives, including profitability, productivity, market share, growth, and overall competitiveness. It serves as a critical indicator of a firm's operational effectiveness and strategic success. Firm performance can be

evaluated through both financial and non-financial metrics, depending on the context, industry, and organizational goals. In financial terms, it is commonly assessed using indicators such as return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), net profit margin, and earnings per share (EPS), which reflect the firm's ability to generate income and utilize resources efficiently (Kaplan & Norton, 2022). In the world of finance, financial performance is measured to give the account of stewardship by the management team to the shareholders. It is a complete evaluation of a company's profitability (Aniagboso & Orjinta, 2023). Beyond financial metrics, firm performance also encompasses non-financial dimensions such as customer satisfaction, employee engagement, innovation, environmental sustainability, and corporate social responsibility. These broader performance indicators are increasingly recognized as essential to long-term value creation, particularly in dynamic and competitive business environments. As a result, firms are adopting balanced scorecards and performance dashboards to capture a more holistic view of their performance (Ittner & Larcker, 2021).

Return on Asset (ROA)

Return on Assets (ROA) is a financial performance metric that measures the ability of a company to generate profit from its assets. It is calculated by dividing net income by total assets and is expressed as a percentage. ROA

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provides insight into how efficiently a company utilizes its assets to generate earnings (Brealey, Myers, & Allen, 2023). A higher ROA indicates that a company is more effectively using its assets to produce profits, whereas a lower ROA suggests inefficiencies or suboptimal asset utilization.

The formula for calculating ROA is: $ROA = \frac{\text{Net Income} \times 100}{\text{Total Assets}}$

Total Assets

ROA is widely used by investors, analysts, and managers to assess operational efficiency and profitability across industries. It provides a snapshot of how well a firm is managing its assets relative to its competitors or the industry average. By comparing the ROA of similar companies or against historical performance, stakeholders can evaluate the effectiveness of asset management and make informed investment or management decisions (Miller & Pesch, 2022).

Return on Equity (ROE)

Return on Equity (ROE) is one of the most widely used financial metrics for evaluating the profitability of a company relative to shareholders' equity. It is calculated by dividing net income by shareholders' equity, with the result expressed as a percentage. ROE is a key indicator of a company's ability to generate profits from its equity capital, making it a critical performance measure for investors and managers alike (Brealey, Myers, & Allen, 2023).

ROE is significant because it indicates how efficiently a company is utilizing its equity capital to generate profits. A high ROE suggests that the company is effectively deploying shareholder funds to create value, while a low ROE may indicate inefficiencies or poor management of equity resources. As such, ROE is used by investors to compare companies within the same industry and to assess the potential return on investment (Eun & Resnick, 2023).

Empirical Review

Aza (2024) ascertained the effect of financial leverage on the performance of Nigerian deposit money banks. The study employed panel data regression model covering the study period of ten years spanning from 2013 to 2022. The study found that debt to asset and equity to asset have significant effect on the ROA while debt to equity has no significant effect on the ROA. The study showed that debt to asset has significant effect on the ROE while debt to equity and equity to asset has no significant effect on the ROE. Setianti and Haryono (2023) examined the effects of product market competition, financial leverage, and financing risk on the stability of Islamic banks in Indonesia between 2018 and 2022. The study used panel regression with E-Views 10 software and the Common Effect Model (CEM) and found that financial leverage and financing risk had a negative impact on banking stability. Mahmood (2023) studied the effect of financial

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leverage on dividend payout ratios in industrial companies listed on the Qatar Stock Exchange, discovered a significant positive relationship between the Debt-to-Assets ratio and the Dividend Payout Ratio. Adhia, Ijaz Khan, Hasan, and Abeydeen (2023) evaluated the factors determining financial leverage on firms listed on the PSX in the chemical industry. E-Views software is used to examine the data, the Huasman test is used to compare panel models, and regression is used to test hypotheses. Profitability and Tax appear to have a considerable positive influence on Financial Leverage. Profitability and tax are the key factors of financial leverage in Pakistan's chemical business, according to the research. Okpunor, Echekoba and Adigwe (2023) ascertained the effect of leverage on the financial performance of selected consumer goods firms quoted in Nigeria Exchange group. The study adopted Ex-post facto longitudinal panel research design. The study revealed that there was a significant positive effect of debt to asset ratio on return on asset of selected quoted consumer goods firm in Nigeria, there was a significant positive effect of debt to equity ratio on return on equity of selected quoted consumer goods firm in Nigeria Exchange group. Nwafor (2023) investigated the effect of financial leverage on firm performance in pharmaceutical industries from 2018 to 2023. Pearson moment correlation was adopted and the study revealed that Debt ratio has significant effect on

performance of pharmaceutical firms in Nigeria, the result of the analysis also include that Total debt to total asset has significant effect on performance of pharmaceutical firms in Nigeria, among other.

Lawani, Tsetim and Enatto (2023) examined the effect of financial leverage on financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. Data were collected from audited annual reports and accounts of 8 listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria from 2013-2022. Data were analyzed using Random Effect Regression. Results indicated that debt-equity ratio and long term debt ratio had had significant negative effect on financial performance while short term debt ratio had negative insignificant effect on financial performance. Abbas and Abubakar (2022) determined the effect of financial leverage on profitability of listed healthcare companies in Nigeria from 2010 to 2019. Using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis and OLS multiple regression analysis, the study found that long-term debt has positive and significant effect on financial performance of listed healthcare companies in Nigeria. Hassan, Kadiri and Oloba (2022) examined the effect of financial leverage on financial performance of selected listed consumer-goods firms in Nigeria from 2010 to 2020. The study employed descriptive statistics and inferential statistics of techniques of data analysis. The study found that any increase in the leverage of a firm in its debt capital mix, the

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return on asset of the firm is negatively impacted. Imeokparia, Adesanmi and Fadipe (2021) ascertained the effect of financial leverage on financial performance of companies from 2009 to 2019. Descriptive, correlation matrix and Pooled Ordinary Least square regression were used to analyze the data obtained. The study showed that total debt ratio and total debt-equity ratio have a strong negative effect on financial performance of selected Deposit Money Banks. Total Debt ratio has insignificant positive effect on financial performance and Total debt to equity ratio is negatively significant on financial performance of selected manufacturing companies in Nigeria.

Methodology

This study adopted *Ex-Post Facto* research design. The design is suitable because the researcher is interested in establishing the causal relationship among the dependent and independent variables. This study adopted purposive sampling technique to select eight (8) industrial goods firms for the study.

The data for this study were obtained from secondary sources. Secondary data is information or data that has previously been collected and recorded for other purposes (Blumberg, Cooper, and Schindler, 2008). The

The modified simple regression estimated model takes the following form:

$$ROA_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DER_{it} + \beta_2 \text{LogAGE}_{\mu it} \dots\dots\dots i$$

$$ROE_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 DER_{it} + \beta_2 \text{LogAGE}_{\mu it} \dots\dots\dots ii$$

Where:

data were extracted from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled firms in Nigeria. The statement of financial position and comprehensive incomes provided data used in computing the selected ratios from 2013-2024. The choice of this period is the year after the mandatory adoption of IFRS for Nigeria (2013).

Model Specification

This study modified the regression models Zaheda (2023) on the relationship between leverage and profitability. The model stated as follows:

$$NPM_{i,t} = t_i + t_1Levi,t + v_2Size_{i,t} + e_i, (1)$$

$$ROA_{i,t} = t_i + t_1Levi,t + v_2Size_{i,t} + e_i, (2)$$

$$ROE_{i,t} = t_i + t_1Levi,t + v_2Size_{i,t} + e_i, (3)$$

Where:

- $NPM_{i,t}$ is net profit divided by net sales for firm i in time t ;
- $ROA_{i,t}$ is EBIT divided by total assets for firm i in time t ;
- ROE_{it} is net profit divided by total shareholders' equity for firm i in time t ;
- $Levit$ is total debt divided by total equity for firm i in time t ;
- $Size_{it}$ is the log of total assets for firm i in time t ;
- Age_{it} is the number of years for firm i in time t ;
- e_i is the error term

The independent variable: Debt to equity and

The dependent variables:

ROA= Return on Assets of firm i in period t

ROE = Return on equity of firm i in period t

AGE =Firm age of firm i in period t

β_0 = slope of the model

β_1, β_2 = coefficient of parameter.

μ_{it} = error term of firm i in period t

Method of Data Analysis

Data Analysis and Results

Table 1: Descriptive Analysis

	DER	ROA	ROE	AGE
Mean	0.098749	-0.033955	-0.036705	38.50000
Median	0.048410	-0.033649	-0.035566	38.50000
Maximum	0.299203	0.003179	0.009732	44.00000
Minimum	0.029090	-0.082990	-0.096754	33.00000
Std. Dev.	0.085766	0.028605	0.033139	3.470174
Skewness	1.160036	-0.237762	-0.309422	0.000000
Kurtosis	3.085026	1.951037	2.143792	1.783217
Jarque-Bera	21.55984	5.305780	4.464237	5.922246
Probability	0.000021	0.070447	0.107301	0.051761
Sum	9.479874	-3.259718	-3.523648	3696.000
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.698806	0.077732	0.104327	1144.000
Observations	96	96	96	96

Interpretation of Descriptive Statistics

The table 1 above showed that the descriptive statistics shows that the mean of debt-equity ratio (DER) of the sampled industrial goods firms is 0.099; the maximum of 0.299 with a minimum of 0.029 and standard deviation of 0.086. The return on assets (ROA) has mean value of -0.034, a standard deviation of 0.029; maximum value of 0.003 with a minimum value of -0.083. The mean of return on equity (ROE) from the sampled observations is -0.037; the standard deviation value is 0.033; a maximum observation of 0.010 with a minimum value of -

Simple Regression Analysis and Pearson Correlation Coefficient were used to analyze the formulated hypotheses with aids of E-view 9.0 at 95% confidence at five degree of freedom (df).

Decision Rule

Reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternate hypothesis (H_1) if the P-value of the test is less than 5% of significance level.

0.097. The mean of firm age (AGE) is 38.500; standard deviation of 3.470; a maximum value of 44.000 with a minimum value of 33.000.

Skewness is the measure of how much the probability distribution of a random variable deviates from the normal distribution. Table 1 outlines that the probability distribution for DER = 0.000; ROA= 0.070; ROE= 0.00107; NPM =0.793; LOGFSZ= 0.050 and AGE = 0.052) are positive and statistically significant at 0.05. From Table above, the Jarque-Bera (JB) which test for normality or the existence of

outlier or extreme values among the variables shows that all our variables are normally distributed and not skewed distribution, significant at 5% level and the result could be generalized.

Table 2: Regression analysis showing the effect between ROA, AGE and DER

Dependent Variable: ROA

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 09/17/25 Time: 16:15

Sample: 2013 2024

Periods included: 12

Cross-sections included: 8

Total panel (balanced) observations: 96

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.111189	1.632616	0.068105	0.9458
DER	0.234994	0.216179	2.087035	0.0299
AGE	-0.017827	0.005263	-3.387231	0.0010
R-squared	0.651963	Mean dependent var		0.098749
Adjusted R-squared	0.640614	S.D. dependent var		0.085766
S.E. of regression	0.051416	Akaike info criterion		-3.056967
Sum squared resid	0.243210	Schwarz criterion		-2.950119
Log likelihood	150.7344	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-3.013777
F-statistic	57.44666	Durbin-Watson stat		1.709789
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Interpretation of Regression Result

In Table 2, R-squared and adjusted Squared values were (0.65) and (0.64) respectively. This indicates that the independent variable explain about 64% of the systematic variations in return on assets of our samples firms over the twelve years periods (2013-2024). The adjusted R², which represents the coefficient of determinations imply that 64% of the total variation in the dependent variable return on assets (ROA) of listed industrial goods firms in

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Debt-equity ratio financing has no significant effect on return on asset of listed Industrial goods firm in Nigeria.

Nigeria is jointly explained by the explanatory variables (DER, and AGE). The F- statistics value of 57.447 with an associated Prob.>F = 0.000 indicates that the model is fit to explain the relationship expressed in the study model and further suggests that the explanatory variables are properly selected, combined and used. The value of adjusted R² of 64% also shows that 36% of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by other factors not captured in the study model.

Test of Autocorrelation: using Durbin-Waston (DW) statistics which we obtained from our regression result in table 2, it is observed that DW statistics is 1.710 and an Akika Info Criterion and Schwarz Criterion which are 3.057 and 2.950 respectively also further confirms that our model is well specified.

Table 2 indicates that debt-equity ratio has a positive and significant effect on return on assets of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. This can be observed from the beta coefficient (β_1) of 0.234994 with t-statistic of 2.087035 which is positive effect at 5% level of significance.

Since the P-value of the test was 0.029 less than 0.05 (5%), this study upholds that debt-equity ratio has a positive and significant effect on return on assets of industrial goods firms in

Nigeria Thus, null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis accepted.

Hypothesis Two

H₀₂: Debt-equity ratio has no significant effect on return on equity of listed Industrial goods firm in Nigeria.

Table 3: Regression analysis showing the effect between ROE, AGE and DER

Dependent Variable: ROE

Method: Panel Least Squares

Date: 09/17/25 Time: 16:16

Sample: 2013 2024

Periods included: 12

Cross-sections included: 8

Total panel (balanced) observations: 96

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.404230	1.659011	-0.243657	0.8080
DER	0.084698	0.190437	2.444758	0.6575
AGE	-0.016136	0.005370	-3.004634	0.0034
R-squared	0.648249	Mean dependent var		0.098749
Adjusted R-squared	0.636779	S.D. dependent var		0.085766
S.E. of regression	0.051689	Akaike info criterion		-3.046353
Sum squared resid	0.245805	Schwarz criterion		-2.939505
Log likelihood	150.2249	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-3.003163
F-statistic	56.51633	Durbin-Watson stat		1.810711

Prob(F-statistic) 0.000000

Interpretation of Regression Result

In Table 3, R-squared and adjusted Squared values were (0.648) and (0.637) respectively. This indicates that the independent variable debt-equity ratio explain about 64% of the systematic variations in return on equity of our samples firms over the twelve years periods (2013-2024). The adjusted R², which represents the coefficient of determinations imply that 64% of the total variation in the dependent variable return on equity (ROE) of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria is jointly explained by the explanatory variables (DER and AGE). The F-statistics value of 56.516 with an associated Prob.>F = 0.000 indicates that the model is fit to explain the relationship expressed in the study model and further suggests that the explanatory variables are properly selected, combined and used. The value of adjusted R² of 64% also shows that 36% of the variation in the dependent variable is explained by other factors not captured in the study model.

Test of Autocorrelation: using Durbin-Waston (DW) statistics which we obtained from our regression result in table 3, it is observed that DW statistics is 1.811 and an Akika Info Criterion and Schwarz Criterion which are 3.046 and 2.940 respectively also further confirms that our model is well specified.

Table 3 indicates that debt-equity ratio has a positive and significant effect on return on equity of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

This can be observed from the beta coefficient (β_1) of 0.084698 with t-statistic of 2.444758 which is positive effect at 5% level of significance.

Since the P-value of the test was 0.029 less than 0.05 (5%)., this study upholds that return on equity has a positive and significant effect on debt-equity ratio of industrial goods firms in Nigeria Thus, null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The study p-value showed 0.029 which is less than 0.05 (5%)., this study upholds that debt-equity ratio has a positive and significant effect on return on assets of industrial goods firms in Nigeria. This result is in line with Aza (2024) who revealed that debt to asset and equity to asset has significant effect on the ROA while debt to equity has no significant effect on the ROA.. However, the study disagreed with Ivo and Anyanwaokoro (2019) who showed that Debt Ratio and Debt to Equity Ratio has negative insignificant effect on Return on Assets (ROA) of quoted cement manufacturing firms in Nigeria. On the other hand Interest Coverage Ratio (ICR) has positive and insignificant effect on return on assets of quoted cement firms in Nigeria.

The result indicates p-values of 0.029 which is less than 0.05 (5%), this study upholds that debt-equity ratio has a positive and significant

effect on return on equity of industrial goods firms in Nigeria. This finding agreed with the finding of Arhinful and Radmehr (2023) who found that both the cash coverage ratio and interest coverage ratio had a positive and statistically significant effect whereas return on equity (ROE). Okpunor, Echekoba and Adigwe (2023) also indicated that debt to asset has significant effect on the ROE while debt to equity and equity to asset has no significant effect on the ROE.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The study ascertained the effect of financial leverage on financial performance of listed Nigerian Industrial goods firm, using debt-equity ratio as the independent variable while return on assets, and return on equity. Data were sources from the eight (8) sampled industrial goods firms in Nigeria spanning from 2013 to 2024. The study employed regression analysis to test the hypotheses. The study revealed that debt-equity ratio has positive significant effect on return on assets and return on equity. The study therefore concluded that financial leverage has significant effect on financial performance in Nigerian industrial goods firm. Based on the findings, the study recommended that the capital-intensive required more expensive equipment which raises the nominal value of the firm's assets as compared to service providing firms.

References

- Abubakar, A., & Garba, A. (2019). Financial leverage and financial performance of quoted services firms in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Technology & Development*, 4(2), 8–13.
- Adam H. (2021). Leverage. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/l/leverage.asp>.
- Adegbite, O., & Oluwatosin, A. (2020). *The impact of financial leverage on firm performance in Nigeria. Journal of Finance and Economic Research*, 8(3), 77–91.
- Adhia, A. A. A., Ijaz, M. M. I. M. M., Khan, R. A. K. R. A., Hasan, A. H. A., & Abeydeen, Z. A. Z. (2023). Financial Leverage and Firm Performance: An Empirical Evidence from Pakistani Chemical Sector. *Psocial sciences*, 3(1), 72-84.
- Afolabi, A. A., & Laseinde, O. T. (2022). *The impact of debt financing on firm performance in Nigeria: Evidence from listed manufacturing firms. Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 8(2), 45–58. <https://doi.org/10.36717/jafm.2022.0208>

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<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

Afolabi, A., & Laseinde, O. T. (2021). Capital structure and firm performance: Empirical evidence from manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 10(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.5923/j.ijfa.20211001.01>

Arhinful, R., & Radmehr, M. (2023). The Impact of Financial Leverage on the Financial Performance of the Firms Listed on the Tokyo Stock Exchange. *Sage Journals*, 1-22.

Aza, I. E. (2024) Effect of financial leverage on the performance of Nigerian deposit money banks. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management* . 10(9), E-ISSN 2504-8856 P-ISSN 2695-2211 2024 www.iiardjournals.org IIARD – International Institute of Academic Research and Development Page 269

Brealey, R. A., Myers, S. C., & Allen, F. (2023). *Principles of corporate finance* (14th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.

Damodaran, A. (2023). *Applied corporate finance* (5th ed.). Wiley.

Eun, C. S., & Resnick, B. G. (2023). *International financial management* (10th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.

Frank, M. Z., & Goyal, V. K. (2022). *Capital structure decisions: Theory and evidence*. *Journal of Financial Perspectives*, 10(2), 101–121.

Hassan, U. U., Kadiri, K. I., & Oloba, U. C. (2022). The effect of financial leverage on the performance of selected listed firms in Nigeria. *Gusau Journal Of Business Administration (GUJOBA)*.

Imeokparia, L., Adesanmi, D., & Fadipe, O. (2021). Effect of financial leverage on financial performance: A comparative study of deposit money banks and manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *Global Journal of Accounting*, 7(1), 37-46.

Ittner, C. D., & Larcker, D. F. (2021). *Assessing the strategic performance of organizations: The use of balanced scorecards*. *Strategic Management Journal*, 42(5), 1023–1045. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.3275>

Kaplan, R. S., & Norton, D. P. (2022). *The balanced scorecard: Translating strategy into action* (Updated ed.). Harvard Business Review Press.

Akaegbobi, Tochukwu N. and Okeke, Onyekachi N.

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B. J. Int. J. A. Econ. Fin. & Acc.

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Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

- Khan, M., & Ali, H. (2023). *Risk analysis in leveraged firms using financial forecasting tools*. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 16(4), 123–135. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm16040123>
- Lawani, B. A., Tsetim, J. T., & Enatto, H. (2023). Effect of financial leverage on financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Production, Operations Management and Economics*, 36, 29-39.
- Modigliani, F., & Miller, M. H. (1958). *The cost of capital, corporation finance and the theory of investment*. *American Economic Review*, 48(3), 261–297.
- Mahmood, S. H. (2023). The effect of financial leverage on dividend payout ratio: an applied study for industrial companies listed on the Qatar Stock Exchange. *World Economics & Finance Bulletin (WEFB)*, 27, 1-11.
- Nwafor, I. S. (2023). Effect of Financial Leverage on Corporate Performance of Pharmaceutical Industries in Nigeria. *Social scientia: Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 8(4).
- Nwankwo, F. O., & Uche, C. A. (2023). Financial leverage and profitability of selected quoted firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Accounting and Financial Management*, 9(2), 45–56.
- Okonkwo, O., & Eze, A. (2021). *Leverage and productivity in the Nigerian manufacturing sector*. *Journal of Economic Studies and Research*, 12(1), 1–15.
- Okoye, L. U., & Ezeaku, H. C. (2022). Capital structure and corporate performance in Nigerian manufacturing firms. *International Journal of Management and Applied Research*, 9(1), 27–41. <https://doi.org/10.18646/2056.91.22-003>
- Okpunor, L., Echekoba, F. N., & Adigwe, P. K. (2023). Effect of leverage on the financial performance of selected quoted consumer goods firms in Nigeria exchange group. *African Banking and Finance Review Journal*, 3(3), 312-322.
- Oladeji, T., & Babalola, K. (2021). *Debt financing and firm performance: Evidence from selected Nigerian listed firms*. *International Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 9(1), 59–70.
- Rahman, M. A., & Adenuga, O. A. (2023). *Ownership dilution and firm control:*

Akaegbobi, Tochukwu N. and Okeke, Onyekachi N.

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Advance Scholars Publication

Published by International Institute of Advance Scholars Development

<https://aspjournals.org/Journals/index.php/bijaefa>

Evidence from equity issuance in West African markets. West African Journal of Business and Management, 10(4), 110–126.

Ross, S. A., Westerfield, R. W., & Jordan, B. D. (2022). *Fundamentals of corporate finance* (14th ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.

Setianti, D. I., & Haryono, S. (2023). Product market competition, financial leverage, risk of financing on financial stability: studies on Islamic Banks in Indonesia. *Journal of Islamic Economics Theory and Application, 10(4), 365-376.*

Udo, E. J., & Akpan, M. O. (2022). The effect of capital structure on firm performance in Nigeria: Evidence from the oil and gas sector. *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development, 13(6), 89–97.*

Will, K. (2021). Borrowed funds. <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/b/borrowed-capital.asp>

Yusuf, M. A., & Bello, K. M. (2022). *Green bonds and alternative debt instruments in emerging markets: Implications for sustainable development in Africa. African Journal of Finance and Economic Development, 7(3), 29–44.*

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